

EDUCATIONAL REFORMS IN THE ARMED FORCES SYSTEM

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Abstract. *This article discusses the military, socio-economic and strategic issues of the new system of the Armed Forces of Uzbekistan.*

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Today, the international relations in some regions are becoming more and more complicated, there are various national-ethnic, religious disagreements in more than two hundred countries, and the deepening of various conflicts between peoples and states, and even the danger of nuclear threats is the main factor of our country's policy. The large-scale reforms carried out by President Shavkat Mirziyoyev show that the principles of peace and stability exist. Uzbekistan is strengthening economic, social and political cooperation not only with Central Asia, but also with the countries of the world from a strategic point of view. The love of the people living in our society for the Motherland is manifested through mother's love and father's courage. Homeland is the soil where the umbilical blood of a person is shed, a blessed place that brings him to maturity and gives meaning to his life. We glorify the Motherland through the great legacy and unforgettable memory left from ancestors to generations. The pride of a person who lives with the feeling of the Motherland is high, his goals and objectives are clear. The prosperity of the country and the peace of the country are a priceless blessing. At all stages of human development, humanity has been striving for peace and harmony. The Uzbek people highly value peace and stability. He knows that his dream is the guarantee of the realization of his aspirations. That is why every citizen living in this country protects the right to live freely and prosperously. By being loyal to the motherland, respecting the heritage of the ancestors, and being worthy of the whole of humanity, they approach every big and small task with responsibility. Thus, strengthening the borders of the country, strengthening the inviolability of our borders, fighting against internal and external threats always calls for awareness. Therefore, the government of Uzbekistan had its own army from the first days of independence. Today, it is the duty of every person living in this country to strengthen the independence of our country, protect its peace and ensure its stable development. In this regard, the issue of youth is at the top. The reason is that in today's modern conditions, serious attention is being paid to the priority issues of educating young people in the spirit of military patriotism. That's why young people brought up in the spirit of military patriotism are ready to lay down their lives for the peace and tranquility of their country. If the feeling of patriotism does not prevail in people's hearts, they cannot be trusted in any field. To turn our national army into a school of bravery, fortitude and courage of the youth, to inculcate in the consciousness of the citizens that service to the Motherland is the highest happiness, and in this way, even an ordinary stone and an

ordinary stone on the soil of the Motherland are sacred. The concept that it is the greatest happiness to be worthy of our ancestors who breathed the memory of the homeland must become our main idea. Therefore, on November 22, 1993, the presidential decree "On the combat flag of the Armed Forces of the Republic of Uzbekistan" was signed, and a single example of the combat flag of the Armed Forces was established. According to the Law of the Supreme Council of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated December 29, 1993 "On Establishing the Day of Defenders of the Fatherland", "January 14 is the Day of Defenders of the Fatherland". The military doctrine of the Republic of Uzbekistan, which was adopted in August 1995, defined the military policy of the country, which was only 4 years old after its independence. Based on the military and political situation in the region, on February 3, 2000, the Defense Doctrine of the Republic of Uzbekistan was adopted. On January 9, 2018, the new version of the Law on the Defense Doctrine of the Republic of Uzbekistan was signed. The doctrine consists of 4 sections and 40 points, which cover general rules, military-political aspects, and military-strategic aspects.

The military doctrine forms the basis of the defense policy of the Republic of Uzbekistan. National security is a component of the concept of the whole state and is based on completely new approaches to the issues of foreign policy, interstate relations, and problems of war and peace. Also, the reliable defense capability of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the high combat capability of the Armed Forces are the most important principles for the development of economic, political, strategic and military-technical and scientific power, the cohesion of the people of Uzbekistan and the education of every citizen in the spirit of patriotism.

Also, on February 23, 2018, the decision of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On approving the concept of educating young people in the spirit of military patriotism" was adopted [1].

In short, educating the youth of our country in the spirit of military patriotism is one of the most important tasks.

Our ancestors who lived in our great past, our great compatriots who defended our country from invaders in order to maintain the peace of our people, fought valiantly against the enemy for the freedom of the Motherland - Shiroq, To`maris, Spitamen, Jalaluddin Manguberdi, Temur Malik, Najmuddin Kubro, Amir We are always proud to always show the bravery of our national heroes like Temur as an example to our military personnel. Currently, our Armed Forces have improved significantly in terms of organization and structure. The mobility of structures, combat capability, and physical and moral readiness of the military have increased. Military units and divisions were provided with modern weapons and combat equipment. The work being carried out to fill our national army with professional personnel, to further improve the training, knowledge and skills of military personnel is commendable.

The President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Commander-in-Chief of the Armed Forces Shavkat Mirziyoyev, on January 12, 2021, during the regular meeting of the Security Council, the work carried out within the framework of the implementation of the tasks and the socio-economic and moral well-being of military personnel serving in the military units emphasized to focus on educational status [2].

The head of our state made it a task to constantly pay attention to the improvement of the moral and spiritual training of military personnel. The work on the organization of military-patriotic and spiritual-educational activities aimed at increasing the sense of pride of the military personnel in their national and cultural heritage on the example of the great thinkers of the Uzbek

people in the troops of the Ministry of Defense emphasizing that the scope should not be removed from the agenda, he expressed the opinion that "there is no military knowledge without military science".

In particular, in the Strategy of Actions on the five priority directions of the development of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2017-2021, implemented at the initiative of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev, ensuring security, inter-ethnic harmony and religious tolerance, combating terrorism, extremism and information threats as important tasks is set. In addition, in his speech at the 72nd session of the United Nations General Assembly in September 2017, the head of state stated that "Our main task is to create the necessary conditions for young people to show their potential, to prevent the spread of the virus of the idea of violence." In this sense, the head of our state suggested countries to develop the UN International Convention on the Rights of Youth, and a special resolution of the UN General Assembly entitled "Enlightenment and Religious Tolerance" was adopted. Also, on February 22, 2021, President Shavkat Mirziyoyev gave a speech at the 46th session of the UN Human Rights Council about the deepening of democratic changes in Uzbekistan and the priorities of the Council's activities. He spoke about the issues of gender policy, attention to ensuring the rights of people with special needs, protecting the rights of young people, ending forced labor and child labor in our country.

The issues of social protection of military personnel, correction of family conditions, provision of housing are being implemented step by step.

In conclusion, the sense of patriotism is strengthened through understanding, feeling and perception of the military sphere. That is why we believe that it is necessary to teach a subject related to the military field once a week in three stages of continuous education. These are in schools, secondary and higher educational institutions...

One of our biggest tasks is to protect peace and tranquility, kindness, mutual respect, inter-ethnic harmony in our country. Therefore, it is necessary to emphasize that we should not forget the difficult trials that our country has gone through during the nearly thirty-three years of independent development, and that each of us should always fight to preserve our independence and peaceful life.

Let's not go too far, in today's world, the people of the world recognize and respect the state and people who live with their dignity, pride and honor, believe in their strength and power, build their future and protect their country with their hard work and intelligence.

In today's world, when the world has become a battlefield of ideologies, it is impossible to ignore the efforts to conquer the thinking of human consciousness. In order to further strengthen the peace and well-being of our Holy Motherland, and the unity of our people, it is necessary for all of us to be always alert, aware, to appreciate the value of today's peaceful days and to protect it like the apple of an eye.

Peace is an important factor of well-being, there is prosperity in a peaceful country, and peace does not leave a prosperous country. Thanks to the honor of independence and the wise policy of the leader of our country, we are enjoying happy days. Our people are engaged in great creative work to build a great state. Strengthening the position of the characteristics of our nation, such as kindness, harmony, and mutual respect in our society, and inculcating them in the minds and hearts of the young generation is an important criterion for our future to be brighter and for our noble goals to be met. Therefore, it is the civic and filial duty of each of us to strengthen peace, which is the greatest wealth of our country, and to always protect it.

A number of tasks are set before us in order to preserve such advancements in our country, peace and tranquility of our people. For example, to study the historical heritage left to us by our great ancestors, to preserve and develop them like the apple of an eye, to strive for spiritual and educational maturity, to contribute to the development of the Motherland and the peace of the country by widely using the achievements of new information technologies.

In order to preserve the peaceful and prosperous life of our free and prosperous country, our hardworking people, and to protect it from outsiders, every boy and girl, following the example of the rich spiritual courage of our great ancestors Najmuddin Kubro, Jalaluddin Manguberdi, Amir Temur, Alisher Navoi, Zahiruddin Muhammad Babur, should fight for peace.

Today, it is necessary to protect young people from various currents and foreign ideas that threaten our society, to form a healthy immunity and worldview in them, to increase the political culture and legal consciousness of the population, which is the main condition of a free civil society. Today, not only state agencies, but also civil society institutions, especially political parties, should approach these tasks with great responsibility, make wide use of the legal opportunities created in this regard, and take a new approach to propaganda work.

Today, young people are receiving a lot of information. Teaching them to analyze information, distinguish between good and bad news is the most important task of every intellectual and parents. Today, if we constantly monitor the educational process and work performance of our children, if we encourage their achievements, explain their shortcomings and establish a friendly relationship, the representatives of the younger generation will certainly acquire spiritual, political, and economic knowledge. With his knowledge and thinking, he easily surpasses the youth of the developed country.

So, the reforms implemented in our country today and the achievements achieved during the years of independence, objective analysis of existing problems, appropriate conclusion and drawing of lessons show the increasing necessity and importance of the national idea. As we promote the reforms implemented in our country through public organizations and non-governmental non-profit organizations, we must turn the development of the new Uzbekistan into a practical and effective action together with the socialization of people.

At the core of all the work carried out in our country is the improvement of the way of life, life and spiritual world of this people, and putting the factors of stability, consistency and quality at the main level in the activities of every field. People living in society must first have a clear goal and a path leading to it. A person should be in constant motion, search, discover new opportunities, and through it create good living conditions not only for himself, but also for those around him, and contribute to the development of society and the state.

Increasing the effectiveness of the ongoing reforms is aimed at creating favorable conditions for rapid development of the state and society in all aspects, raising the development of our country to a higher level and ensuring stable competition with the world community. That's why an implemented Action and Development strategy is key to our massive fundamental progress spanning the next hundred years.

It is the right of our multi-ethnic people to live in peace that is at the root of all actions that ensure legality and justice in the mutual relations between man and power, society and the state. Also, the launch of "Generosity and Support" charity work during the quarantine period is one of the most important aspects of the principle of humanity. Therefore, every citizen living in our country should live with the spirit of faith in the society. After all, our respected President Shavkat

Mirziyoyev said, "It is well known to all of us that we cannot imagine human interests in isolation from peace of the country, mutual respect, kindness and harmony in our society. All this is our priceless wealth and it is our sacred duty to keep it like the apple of our eye.

New Uzbekistan is moving from development to development. The essence of the wide-scale reforms implemented under the leadership of President Shavkat Mirziyoyev calls people to understand and feel their human factor in life and their internal capabilities more deeply, and not to shy away from work. The spiritual and physical maturity of citizens, especially the youth of the country, the feeling of high civic responsibility through the idea of the development of the country, the peace of the country and the well-being of the people, and the harmony with the sense of direct commitment to the society are our great goals. will be a solid foundation for its implementation [3, p. 187-198]. Also, in the new reforms of Uzbekistan, we are moving from a strategy of action to a strategy of development. National pride, courage and devotion to duty are the order of the day.

REFERENCES

1. The decision of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On approving the concept of educating young people in the spirit of military patriotism". People's Word newspaper, February 24, 2018.
2. President Shavkat Mirziyoyev's speech at the next meeting of the Security Council. "Vatanparvar" newspaper, January 15, 2021.
3. Mamatqabilov T.D. "Educational foundations of the concept of continuous spiritual education" - T.: "Academy", 2022.-B.37-38.
4. Mamatqobilov T.D. "National Idea: Development Strategy of Uzbekistan". - T.: "Academy", 2021. - B.187-198.
5. Mamatqabilov T. et al. OVERCOMING GLOBAL PROBLEMS AND DEVELOPMENT STRATEGIES //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. B10. – C. 230-234.
6. Mirziyoyev Sh.M. "For human dignity, his rights and freedoms, legal interests" - T.:Uzbekistan, 2022 - year.-B.371.
7. Mirziyoyev Sh.M. "Strategy of New Uzbekistan". T.: Uzbekistan, 2021. - B.237.
8. Khusenov, T. Khafizov, T. Mamatqabilov, D. Sayfullayeva KEY TRENDS IN SUPPLY PEACE AND RESTORATION // SAI. 2023. №B10. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/key-trends-in-supply-peace-and-restoration> (дата обращения: 06.01.2024).
9. Speech of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev at the 78th session of the UN General Assembly. "Khalk sozi" newspaper, September 20, 2023 - B.1-2.
10. Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Part of the introduction. - T.: Uzbekistan, 2023. - B.3-4.